

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Spatiotemporal dynamics of nanosecond pulsed discharge in the form of a fast ionization wave: self-consistent two-dimensional modeling and comparison with experiments under negative and positive polarity

To cite this article: Konstantinos Kourtzanidis and Svetlana M Starikovskaia 2025 *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **58** 195202

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [The dynamics of discharge propagation and x-ray generation in nanosecond pulsed fast ionisation wave in 5 mbar nitrogen](#)
Bangdou Huang, Cheng Zhang, Jintao Qiu et al.
- [TALIF measurements of oxygen atom density in the afterglow of a capillary nanosecond discharge](#)
A V Klochko, J Lemaire, J P Booth et al.
- [Scaling of pulsed nanosecond capillary plasmas at different specific energy deposition](#)
Yifei Zhu, Svetlana M Starikovskaia, Natalia Yu Babaeva et al.

The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

ECS UNITED

247th ECS Meeting
Montréal, Canada
May 18-22, 2025
Palais des Congrès de Montréal

Early registration deadline: April 21, 2025

Unite with the ECS Community

Spatiotemporal dynamics of nanosecond pulsed discharge in the form of a fast ionization wave: self-consistent two-dimensional modeling and comparison with experiments under negative and positive polarity

Konstantinos Kourtzanidis^{1,*}

¹ Chemical Process & Energy Resources Institute (CPERI), Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH), 6th km Charilaou-Thermi, Thermi 57001 Thessaloniki, Greece

² Laboratory of Plasma Physics (CNRS, Ecole Polytechnique, Univ. Paris-Sud, Observatoire de Paris, Sorbonne Université, l'Institut Polytechnique de Paris), Ecole Polytechnique, route de Saclay, 91128 Palaiseau, France

E-mail: kourtzanidis@certh.gr

Received 6 February 2025, revised 24 March 2025

Accepted for publication 9 April 2025

Published 17 April 2025

CrossMark

Abstract

Nanosecond discharges are characterized by a shift in energy branching toward the excitation of electronic levels and dissociation, making them particularly attractive for plasma chemistry. Understanding the spatio-temporal structure of these discharges is especially important. This paper presents a detailed 2D-axisymmetric numerical analysis of a nanosecond discharge propagating in a long tube and in pure nitrogen. The modeling is conducted using a self-consistent plasma fluid solver under the local mean energy approximation, including photoionization. The discharge develops at moderate pressures, 1–10 Torr, in the form of a fast ionization wave (FIW). Simulations are performed for both negative and positive polarities of the voltage pulse applied to the high-voltage electrode. The computational results are validated against available experimental data, including FIW velocity within the studied pressure range,

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

Original Content from this work may be used under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Any further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the title of the work, journal citation and DOI.

electron density, longitudinal electric field, and the radial distribution of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ emission on a nanosecond timescale.

Keywords: nanosecond discharge, fast ionization wave, plasma modeling, self-consistent simulation, low-temperature plasma, pulsed discharge

1. Introduction

Nanosecond discharges have gained popularity in recent decades, due to their unique properties related to plasma chemistry: the energy branching in these discharges is shifted toward excitation of electronically excited species and dissociation by electron impact. The availability of commercially produced nanosecond high-voltage (HV) generators (HVGs), the development of pulse measurement techniques, ‘ordinariness’ of pico- and femtosecond laser measurements [1, 2] have rendered nanosecond plasma no longer exotic, which is currently studied for a wide variety of applications, such as plasma-assisted combustion and detonation [3–5], plasma-assisted aerodynamics [6, 7], plasma medicine [8], nitrogen fixation [9] and many more. These applications require an understanding of the spatio-temporal structure of discharge development, often in chemically active mixtures (e.g. in the case of combustion or detonation). Such an understanding can be achieved through plasma modeling, validated against a broad set of experimental data.

The nanosecond discharge in long tubes was first reported in 1893 by Thomson [10]. He investigated the propagation of a luminous front in a 15 m glass tube between two vessels with mercury, which were the electrodes and the constructive parts of a mercury pump. The voltage at the HV electrode was a pulse with a calculated decay of about a hundred nanoseconds. Measured using a rotating mirror, the propagation speed of the luminescence front was estimated to be ‘approximately half the speed of light’.

Since then, interest in nanosecond discharges has been renewed every 20–30 years, in correlation with the development of experimental techniques and theoretical approaches. Works on nanosecond discharges of the XX century are reviewed in [11]. Therein, the authors suggest the term ‘fast ionization wave’ (FIW) for nanosecond discharges developing in long tubes (the length of the tube is much bigger than the diameter of the tube) and propagating with a velocity of a few centimeters per nanosecond. The review includes description of dynamics of the propagation of the FIWs generated by HV pulses from a few kilovolts to a few hundreds of kilovolts and duration of a few tens of nanoseconds. Velocities of the FIW propagation in different gases, from nitrogen, air and helium to quite exotic like SF_6 , CCl_4 or acetone vapors are presented. Non-local effects in the FIWs front, influence of high-energy electrons on the formation and motion of FIWs are discussed. Theoretical models of FIWs at that time mainly described one-dimensional distribution of the electric field and of current in plasma, special attention being attributed to the run-away electrons in the front of nanosecond discharges at low and moderate pressures.

In the period 1994–2008, a series of papers on the FIWs was published (see for example, [12–18]), a part of them being summarized in [19, 20]. The papers were devoted to experimental study of the FIWs in so-called kinetic approach when the main interest of study is how to link electrical parameters measured in plasma (the electric field, the electric current, the deposited energy) to the energy branching in the discharge and the efficiency of plasma-chemical processes. The FIWs were triggered in long tubes by pulses of units-tens of kV at moderate pressures, 0.1–100 Torr.

In particular, it was shown that the peak of high reduced fields [17] in the front of the FIW, up to several kTd ($1 \text{ Td} = 10^{-17} \text{ V}\cdot\text{cm}^2$), does not exceed two to three nanoseconds in duration. Then the field decreases sharply to hundreds of Td, optimal for excitation of electronically excited levels of atoms and molecules [13, 17]. In the pressure range from units of Torr to tens of Torr, optimal for the development of fast ionization waves, the peak value of the electric field E increases less than twofold; the reduced electric field E/N decreases almost by an order of magnitude. It was shown, by means of numerical calculations, that at the FIW front, the electron energy distribution function, EEDF, is close to the distribution formed at relaxation of the electron beam in the gas media with predominance of high energy electrons responsible for the homogeneous organization of the gas [19]. At the same time, the main production of electrons and major energy deposition occur behind the front of the FIW, 5–10 ns after the peak. In nitrogen environments, controlling the nanosecond pulse width has been proven to be very important for enhancing the efficiency of nitrogen vibrational excitation [9], which underlines the importance of the pulse shape on the obtained plasma chemistry.

The progress in numerical modeling during the two last decades opened possibilities for more detailed description of nanosecond discharges. Topical review [21] considers sub-nanosecond breakdown in atmospheric pressure gases. The authors of the review claim that, even if numerical simulation of fast pulsed discharges does not reproduce all the complexity of the physical processes involved in the discharge development (i) it provides a much wider set of discharge characteristics comparing to experimental measurements; (ii) it allows easier than in experiment, sensitivity analysis revealing the main factors responsible for the observed phenomena. Finally, it is a synergy of experimental measurements and numerical modeling which provides better understanding of the physical event under study.

As described in the review [11], the first theoretical/numerical investigations of FIWs date back to the late 1970s and early 1980s Soviet era. These studies were based on one-dimensional fluid (hydrodynamic) or long-wavelength

approximations and self-similar solutions were obtained for the FIW propagation, which inherently assumes constant properties in the plasma front. In the same review paper, a more general one-dimensional approach based on the telegraph and total current equations is also described which has been used to describe and comprehend several features of the FIW development. Since then, and besides some very interesting theoretical/analytical studies on the solutions of streamer-like planar fronts [22] and FIW propagation in long shielded tubes [23], several one-dimensional models (both kinetic and fluid based) have been used to describe FIWs. Acknowledging the large computational cost of a kinetic description of plasmas based on particles [24, 25] (either using a Monte-Carlo-Collision or Particle In Cell method), which require the solution of the Boltzmann equation to describe the behavior of single particle species, and its dramatic increase in 2D systems despite recent advancements [26], most of FIW numerical studies incorporate the fluid (macroscopic) approximation, where macroscopic quantities such as density, mean velocity and mean energy are used to describe the particle species behavior and which correspond to velocity moments of the Boltzmann equation (and relevant closure approximations). The corresponding computational cost is largely reduced compared to kinetic approaches, while the solution of the system of fluid equations (momentum, continuity, energy) can leverage efficient algorithms and discretization schemes on Cartesian or unstructured meshes, from the very active computational fluid dynamics (CFD) community. Further assumptions lead to more simplified (and thus computationally efficient) models: neglecting inertia terms in the momentum equation (focusing on non-magnetized plasma), assuming isothermal conditions and collisionality, we derive the drift-diffusion model (see section 3 for details), where each species evolution is governed by a single continuity equation in a convection-diffusion-reaction form self-consistently coupled with the electric field through the Poisson equation. Transport and reaction rates depend non-linearly on the reduced electric field under the local field approximation (LFA—1st order moment model) or the mean electron energy under the local mean energy approximation (LMEA—2nd order moment model). Under the LMEA, non-local effects owed to a considerable variation of the electric field over the electron energy relaxation length are accounted for and the model requires the inclusion of an equation for the electron mean energy.

One of the first two-dimensional numerical studies of regular ionization waves in long tubes was performed by Brok *et al* [27] in 2003. The authors studied the development of anode directed, DC-excited ionization waves sustained by thermionic emission in moderate pressure (few Torr) Argon and demonstrated the capabilities of fluid modeling to qualitatively capture the breakdown and propagation mechanism, while emphasized the importance of dielectric surface charging. The influence of surface charges and memory effects in such rather slow ionization waves have recently been investigated [28] both experimentally and numerically. FIWs have been studied self-consistently in dry air and nitrogen [29, 30] but also in Helium [31] and in millimeter and capillary

tubes in low pressure N₂ discharges [32–35], and very recently in short gaps in air and CO₂ [36]. Effects of field emission and relative influence of runaway electrons have been studied with 1D PIC simulations for atmospheric pressure nitrogen [37, 38]. Although this list of numerical works related to FIWs is not exhaustive, it showcases that in the current state of numerical models and high performance computing infrastructure, fluid modeling is the typical method for two-dimensional simulations of FIWs. Nevertheless, the computational cost of fluid models is strongly linked on the highly discrepant nature of spatial and temporal timescales of FIWs as well as the dimensions of the simulated discharge region. Accurate, robust and efficient time integration schemes are necessary to account for the extremely different temporal timescales related to electrons and ions drift, assuring that stability (majorly linked to timestep constraints linked to the dielectric relaxation time) is guaranteed. In addition, the development of FIWs in long tubes (several tens of centimeter long as the ones studied in this work), require appropriate meshing in the whole interelectrode gap which renders such 2D simulations extremely time demanding and only possible when parallel computing techniques are efficiently implemented. The influence of photoionization in gases that are known to efficiently produce photons that can ionize neutral molecules (such as oxygen-nitrogen mixtures) adds up to the numerical challenges.

In this work, we present a detailed 2D axisymmetric self-consistent numerical study of nanosecond moderate pressure discharge in nitrogen propagating in a long tube as a FIW. The main goal of this paper is the comparison of self-consistent numerical simulations with the experimental results on FIW propagation obtained within the research group of one of the co-authors and reviewed in [19]. We have deliberately chosen the results which never were a subject of detailed numerical analysis. In particular, the dependence of the FIW velocity and the change in the radial structure of the FIW with pressure depending on the discharge polarity have never been the subject of detailed numerical modeling. Thus, the numerical results are compared with experimental measurements of the FIW propagation velocity, the reduced electric field, the electron density and the N₂(C³Π_u) number density distribution for negative and positive polarities of the applied high voltage pulse. Emphasis is given on both the temporal and spatial development of the discharge, aiming to reveal and understand the particularities of each pulse polarity at different gas pressure inside the 1–10 torr range.

The article is structured as follows: in section 2, we provide a brief overview of the experimental setup and findings. In section 3, we present the physical and numerical models used in this study. In section 4, we present the computational case and numerical parameters. In section 5 we present numerical results on electric current, FIW velocity, spatiotemporal distribution of plasma parameters and produced species, comparing them with experimental findings and discussing the results. In section 6, we elaborate on and discuss main assumptions used in the model. Last, in section 7, we present the conclusions and propose future directions.

Figure 1. Typical scheme of the experimental setup with the main experimental equipment. The general scheme of the experimental setup with the main experimental equipment. TG is triggering generator, HVG is high voltage generator, OSC is oscilloscope, BCS1 and BCS2 are back current shunts, CP is capacitive probe, DT is discharge tube, PMT is photomultiplier tube, ICCD is intensified charge-coupled device (camera), SP is spectrometer, PC is personal computer. Reproduced from [39]. © IOP Publishing Ltd. All rights reserved.

2. A brief information about experimental methods and observed results

A typical experimental scheme is presented in figure 1. In the considered experiments, the HVG is always connected to the discharge tube (DT) by a long HV coaxial cable. For the most of experiments with FIWs at moderate (1–50 Torr) pressures, glass or quartz DTs of different lengths (20–60 cm) and diameters (1–5 cm) are used. Under these conditions, the application of a voltage pulse of 10–50 kV amplitude, a few nanosecond rise time and a few tens of nanoseconds FWHM to the HV electrode, initiates an ionization wave which starts always from the high voltage electrode and propagates along the tube. Typically, experiments incorporate a grounded screen linked to the shielding of the HV cable. However, even in the absence of the screen, the ionization wave can propagate as the current closes over the surrounding space. The end load of the DT can be different, often set to zero or infinity; or the low voltage electrode and the grounded screen can be connected to another coaxial cable. Typically, the nanosecond discharge is highly repetitive, and it is possible to accumulate any signal at low frequencies (5–30 Hz) having a subnanosecond synchronization of the discharge and diagnostics.

Spatial structure of the propagating FIW is studied by subnanosecond ICCD imaging (0.5–2 ns typical ICCD gates). To control the voltage pulse arriving the high voltage electrode, to measure the current through plasma and the deposited energy, calibrated custom made back current shunts (BCSs) are used. They are soldered in the grounded shielding of the high voltage cable between the HVG and the discharge cell so that the incident and reflected from the electrical mismatched load pulses are separated in time. We note here that the voltage on the HV

electrode at the moment of the discharge start is doubled comparing to the voltage in the cable as a result of the constructive interference between the incident pulse and the pulse reflected from the DT due to mismatch of the electrical load: 10 kV in the middle of the long cable provides 20 kV at the HV electrode. A description of the BCS technique in application to nanosecond discharges can be found in [40].

The velocity of the FIW and the longitudinal electric field are measured with the help of calibrated custom made capacitive probes (CPs). The electron density is calculated knowing the current, the field and the drift velocity. Time-resolved behavior of electronically excited species is studied using optical emission spectroscopy with the help of a spectrometer linked to the ICCD camera or to the photomultiplier tube (PMT). All electrical signals are measured by nanosecond oscilloscopes.

A general picture of the development of the nanosecond discharge under mentioned conditions can be summarized as follows: for both negative and positive polarities of the high-voltage pulse, the discharge starts from the high-voltage electrode and propagates with a velocity of a few centimeters per nanosecond [11, 13]. There is a well-defined maximum of the FIW velocity upon pressure. For example, for the voltage amplitude about 10 kV in the cable and the tube diameter of a few centimeters, the maximum velocity is observed around 4 Torr. The position of the maximum shifts to higher pressures as the voltage amplitude increases.

The reduced electric field in the front of the FIW is high, a few kTd [17]. The duration of this high peak is a few nanoseconds which corresponds, for a given velocity of propagation, to centimeters or even tens of centimeters in length. After the high peak of the electric field, the fields optimal for

Figure 2. Development of the fast ionization wave in air for different pressures and polarities of the high-voltage pulse. The diameter of the quartz tube is 17.5 mm; the tube length is 50 cm. ICCD gate is 1 ns; spectral sensitivity is 300–800 nm (see text). Conical high-voltage electrode is on the left-hand side. © [2008] IEEE. Reprinted, with permission, from [15].

excitation of electronic levels of molecules and dissociation, a few hundreds of Td, are usually installed. These fields keep constant or only slightly decreasing up to the end of the high voltage pulse. The first high peak of the electric field during the FIW propagation is responsible for the main initial ionization of the gas, resulting in diffuse plasma. In the constant field after the discharge front the electron density can continue to increase, albeit at a significantly reduced rate.

At the dimensions of DTs and the parameters of the HV pulses mentioned above, the specific energy deposited in gas (SED) is typically small, on the order of 10^{-4} – 10^{-3} eV/molecule. Typical electron densities are $n_e \sim 10^{12}$ – 10^{13} cm $^{-3}$, providing the ionization degree around 10^{-5} – 10^{-4} . This means that the recombination time, 1–10 microseconds, is much longer than the duration of the discharge, and the electron density stays constant in time in the discharge and near afterglow [17].

Although the negative and positive polarity FIWs are similar in physical parameters, they differ essentially in their spatial structure. This was observed for air and for nitrogen. An example of non-filtered ICCD imaging for air is provided by figure 2 [15]. The spectral sensitivity of the PicoStar HR12 (La Vision) ICCD camera and lens was 300–800 nm. In air, the emission over this spectral region is mainly due to the second positive system of molecular nitrogen, $N_2(C^3\Pi_u) \rightarrow N_2(B^3\Pi_g)$ transition [18]. The life time of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ in air at 1–10 Torr is long, 40 – 20 ns [18], still the pattern of discharge is clearly seen. The images present raw experimental data, without the inverse Abel transform. At negative polarity, the emission is stronger near the walls, while at positive polarity, the main emission, especially at low pressures, comes from the near-axis region.

In nitrogen, FIWs have a similar space structure, often with more pronounced difference between the axis and the

near-wall region. This can be seen from ICCD images in rectangular cross-section double-pulse setup [29] or from $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ radial profiles in nanosecond capillary discharge [39].

The observed difference in the spatial patterns of the FIW for each polarity is not well understood until now. Thus, in the following sections we leverage high-fidelity numerical modeling to explain this difference and explain features of the FIW for both polarities at different gas pressure.

3. Numerical modeling

We employ a fluid (continuum) description of the plasma which is the core of the physical model used in the computational software COPAIER [41, 42]—a multi-species and multi-temperature plasma fluid solver allowing for self-consistent description of the plasma spatial and temporal evolution (the main author is a co-developer of the solver). Each of the species, s , considered in the pre-defined plasma-gas chemistry is governed by a continuity equation :

$$\frac{\partial n_s}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\Gamma}_s = S_s, \quad (1)$$

where S_s is the net rate of production of species s due to chemical reactions and it reads:

$$S_s = \sum_r c_{s,r} R_r + S_{ph}, \quad (2)$$

where $c_{s,r}$ is the net number of particles of species s created or lost in one reaction of type r (so it can be positive or negative). Note that S_{ph} is the photo-ionization source term based on the three-group Helmholtz approximation model [43] (see below).

The species number flux $\vec{\Gamma}_s = n_s \vec{v}_s$ is given by the momentum balance equation which is approximated by the drift-diffusion equation :

$$\vec{\Gamma}_s = \text{sgn}(q_s) n_s \mu_s \vec{E} - \vec{\nabla} \cdot (n_s D_s) - n_s \vec{u}, \quad (3)$$

where q_s is the species s charge, μ_s and D_s are the species s mobility and diffusion coefficient respectively, u is the mean mass fluid convection velocity (assumed zero in this study). The electric field is defined as $\vec{E} = -\nabla\Phi$, with Φ being the electrostatic potential defined by the Poisson's equation

$$\nabla \cdot (\epsilon \nabla \Phi) = -\rho = -\sum_s q_s n_s, \quad (4)$$

where ϵ is the dielectric permittivity and ρ is the charge density.

In equation (3) the diffusion coefficient is related to the mobility term by Einstein's relation, $D_s = \mu_s k_B T_s / q$. For electrons and the mean electron energy (see below), transport (mobility μ) and reaction rate coefficients (k) are tabulated with an electric energy dependence under the LMEA. Under the LMEA, transport and rate coefficients depend on the mean electron energy instead of the electric field (LFA) - see section 3.1. for more details on the reaction rates.

To justify our choice of the LMEA over the LFA, we calculate the electron energy relaxation length which can be approximated using [44]:

$$\lambda_e = \sqrt{D_e \tau_e}, \quad (5)$$

where $\tau_e^{-1} = \frac{2m_e}{m_n} \nu + \nu^*$, m_n is the neutral species mass, ν is the elastic collision frequency and ν^* is the inelastic collision frequency. In our conditions, we estimate λ_e in the 5–10 mm range. The discharge gap, L , is 60 cm and most importantly, the FIW front (as we will see below) presents strong gradients of the electric field in length scales that are millimetric, which indicates that non-local effects are important and the validity [45] of the LFA and local field equilibrium is violated.

The mean electron temperature can be obtained by the electron energy conservation given as:

$$\frac{\partial n_e}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\Gamma}_e = S_e, \quad (6)$$

where $n_e = n_e \epsilon$ is the electron energy density and ϵ is the electron mean energy which by assuming that is a results mainly from random motion relates to the electron mean temperature by $k_B T_e = 2/3 \epsilon$.

The electron energy flux reads :

$$\vec{\Gamma}_e = \frac{5}{3} \epsilon \vec{\Gamma}_e + \vec{q}. \quad (7)$$

The heat flux, \vec{q} is assumed proportional to the gradient of the electron mean energy :

$$\vec{q} = -\frac{5}{3} n_e D_e \nabla \epsilon. \quad (8)$$

The source term, S_e includes heating by the electric field (electron Joule heating) and energy losses in inelastic and elastic collisions as:

$$S_e = -e \vec{\Gamma}_e \cdot \vec{E} - \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{react}}} \Delta E_i r_i - \frac{3}{2} k_b n_e \frac{2m_e}{m_g} (T_e - T_g) \nu_m. \quad (9)$$

The first term in the right hand side corresponds to the electron Joule heating term. The second term is the sum for each electron impact reaction, i , of the inelastic electron energy loss, where ΔE_i is the energy threshold (thermal energy loss) in reaction i and r_i is the rate of progress. The summation is performed over the total number of gas-phase reactions, N_{react} . The last term, corresponds to the energy loss due to elastic collisions which can also be approximated with an effective rate coefficient and integrated directly to the inelastic energy loss term. In this last term, ν_m is the electron momentum-transfer frequency, T_g is the gas density, m_g is the heavy species particle mass, m_e is the electron particle mass.

The density of the dominant background species (here N_2) is given by the ideal gas law :

$$p = \sum_s n_s k_B T_s. \quad (10)$$

Surface charge accumulation on dielectric surfaces is taken into account by assuming that particles stick to the dielectric surface and no diffusion occurs. Thus the surface charge is given by:

$$\sigma = \int \vec{j} \cdot \vec{n} dt, \quad (11)$$

where the plasma current density reads :

$$\vec{j} = \sum_s q_s \vec{\Gamma}_s. \quad (12)$$

Lastly, we include a photoionization model involving the solution of three Helmholtz type equations [43] in the form:

$$\nabla^2 S_{\text{ph},j} - (\lambda_j p)^2 = -A_j p^2 I_{\text{ion}} \quad (13)$$

for $j = 1, 3$, where $S_{\text{ph},j}$ is the photoionization source term in m^3/s for equations $j = 1, 3$, the gas mixture pressure is denoted as p and I_{ion} is the ionization rate. The total photoionization source term is then simply given by:

$$S_{\text{ph}} = \sum_{j=1}^3 S_{\text{ph},j}. \quad (14)$$

The six coefficients, λ_j and A_j are exponentially fitting parameters for the photon propagator function which is given as:

$$\frac{\Phi_0}{p} (pr) = (pr) \sum_{j=1}^3 A_j e^{-\lambda_j pr} \quad (15)$$

The function Φ_0 / p has been calculated for pure nitrogen in low pressure using the PHOTOPiC software [46, 47]. The fitting coefficients have been calculated by minimizing an

Table 1. Fitting coefficients for the photoionization three-group Helmholtz model.

j	A_j	λ_j
1	4.6657×10^{-5}	0.51102
2	3.8146×10^{-4}	0.951
3	7.4994×10^{-4}	4.2468

A_j in $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{Torr}^{-2}$
 λ_j in $\text{cm}^{-1}\text{Torr}^{-1}$

ordinary least square cost function and are presented in table 1. Although photoionization occurs more efficiently when small amounts of oxygen are present in the gas as UV photons mainly produced from radiative decay of nitrogen excited species ionize oxygen molecules, the mechanism is present in pure nitrogen [48] also (although poorly understood and studied), and our numerical results showed that its inclusion is important for a correct representation of the FIW propagation speed, especially when a low initial electron density is used. A more elaborated discussion on photoionization effects is given in section 6.

A detailed description of several numerical schemes available in the COPAIER solver can be found in [41, 42, 49]. Here we summarize the main features used in this specific study. A finite volume approach is used to solve the drift-diffusion equations. The Scharfetter-Gummel flux scheme [50] is used here to discretize the convection–diffusion operator of species continuity equations. Temporal integration for the species system of continuity equations is performed via an implicit time-marching algorithm based on the Gauss–Seidel technique [51].

In equations (6) and (9), the evaluation of the energy loss source term explicitly can lead to non-physical oscillations that can damage the stability of the whole system. In order to circumvent this issue, an implicit treatment of the joule heating source terms has been adopted based on [52]. The energy loss source term is treated fully implicitly as well as all electron-impact reaction source terms involving neutral species as reactants. The finite element method has been used to solve the Poisson and Helmholtz equations, with a P1-finite element formulation. A semi-implicit formulation for the Poisson equation, similar to the one proposed in [53] has been implemented, allowing to circumvent the dielectric relaxation timestep constraints. The numerical solver is parallelized based on the MPI paradigm and a non-overlapping domain decomposition method.

3.1. Plasma chemistry model

We choose to use a reduced N_2 -plasma chemistry, where nine (9) modeled species are included, consisting of electrons, positive N_2^+ and N_4^+ ions, neutral N_2 molecules as well as the following excited states: $\text{N}_2(\text{A}^3\Sigma_u^+)$, $\text{N}_2(\text{B}^3\Pi_g)$, $\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)$, $\text{N}_2(\text{a}^1\Sigma_u)$. Sixteen (16) chemical reactions (in addition to photoionization) are taken into account which are listed in table 2. Transport coefficients for electron and electron mean energy equations as well as the reaction rates for R1–R6 have been calculated using the two-term Boltzmann solver, BOLSIG+ [54] including electron-electron, electron-ion and

superelastic collisions and under the exponential growth (PT) model. These transport and rate coefficients have been tabulated with a dependency on the mean electron energy ($f(\epsilon)$). We assume a gas composition of 100% N_2 . The ionization degree is assumed 10^{-5} , the electron density 10^{18} m^{-3} and the gas temperature 300 K. Cross-sections for N_2 used as inputs in BOLSIG+ have been taken from the Phelps database [55] and includes 26 electron-neutral scattering cross sections describing dissociative attachment, effective momentum transfer, ionization, rotational, electronic and vibrational excitation. The direct electron-impact ionization (15.6 eV) cross section dataset has been extended to high electron energies based on [56, 57]. To include associated electron impact energy losses, all excited (rotationally, vibrationally in different levels and electronically) species which are not tracked have been lumped to a single species, denoted as $\text{N}_2(\text{lump})$ which is also not tracked (assumed as N_2). The rate coefficient for R15 is then calculated as follows: we equate the sum of contributions of all these untracked reactions to the inelastic power loss term, with the loss of the fictitious lumped reaction (R15). Assuming that the energy threshold for R15 is 1 eV, we get the following formula for the rate coefficient:

$$k_{\text{lump}} = \sum_{i=1}^n (\Delta E_i k_i), \quad (16)$$

where ΔE_i and k_i are the energy threshold and rate coefficient for reaction i , and n are the total number of excitation reactions (not tracked). N atoms are not tracked (assumed as 0.5 N_2 in R8) as well as vibrationally excited N_2 states (assumed in ground state of N_2). This reduced chemistry set is of course rather simplified but provides a good balance between accuracy and required computational time, allowing us to capture the main features of the FIW dynamics, while stabilizing the numerical algorithm under the LEA scheme, by incorporating the main electron energy loss mechanisms (see section 6 for further elaboration).

Reduced ion mobilities for N_2^+ and N_4^+ (in N_2) have been taken from LxCAT swarm data (Phelps and Viehland databases [55, 58]). Constant (reduced) diffusion coefficient of $1.98 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ was assumed for all neutral species. We neglect gas flow dynamics as their timescales are much larger than the simulation time-scales. The gas temperature (T_g) is assumed constant at 300 K. This is a good approximation on the nanosecond FIW propagation timescales, as (i) we mainly consider the FIW front propagation, at this time scale the heating can be neglected; (ii) the specific energy delivered to plasma is low.

Electrons and positive N_2^+ and N_4^+ ions are initialized with a number density of $2 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and 10^{14} m^{-3} respectively, rest of neutral excited species with a low density of 10^3 m^{-3} while N_2 species initial density is calculated by equation (10) depending on the gas pressure. The initial electron (and ion) density was chosen so that it allows for the initiation of the discharge and for approaching the FIW dynamics (mainly FIW speed) observed in the experiments. In section 6, we elaborate on this choice and try to justify the source of such seed electrons before (or right after) the initiation of the discharge.

Table 2. Chemical reaction model used in the simulations.

Reaction	Rate coefficient	Comment—Source
R1: $e + N_2 \rightarrow N_2^+ + 2e$	$f(\epsilon)$	$\Delta E_i = 15.6$ eV, [55] ^a
R2: $e + N_2 \rightarrow N_2^+ + 2e$	$f(\epsilon)$	$\Delta E_i = 18.8$ eV $N_2^+(B^2\Sigma_u^+)$ excitation, [55] ^a
R3: $e + N_2 \rightarrow N_2(A) + e$	$f(\epsilon)$	v0-4, [55] ^a
R4: $e + N_2 \rightarrow N_2(B) + e$	$f(\epsilon)$	[55] ^a
R5: $e + N_2 \rightarrow N_2(C) + e$	$f(\epsilon)$	[55] ^a
R6: $e + N_2 \rightarrow N_2(a') + e$	$f(\epsilon)$	[55] ^a
R7: $e + N_4^+ \rightarrow N_2 + N_2$	$2 \times 10^{-6}(300/T_e)^{0.5}$	[59] ^b
R8: $e + N_2^+ \rightarrow N + N(2D)$	$2 \times 10^{-7}(300/T_e)^{0.5}$	N atoms not tracked (assumed 0.5 N_2), [59] ^a
R9: $N_2(C) \rightarrow N_2(B) + hv$	2.45×10^7	[60] ^d
R10: $N_2(C) + N_2 \rightarrow N_2(a') + N_2(v)$	1×10^{-11}	Vib. state not tracked (assumed N_2), [59] ^b
R11: $N_2(B) + N_2 \rightarrow N_2(A) + N_2(v)$	1×10^{-11}	Vib. state not tracked (assumed N_2), [59] ^b
R12: $N_2(a') + N_2 \rightarrow N_2(v) + N_2(v)$	2×10^{-13}	Vib. state not tracked (assumed N_2), [59] ^b
R13: $N_2(A) + N_2(A) \rightarrow N_2(C) + N_2(v)$	1.6×10^{-10}	Vib. state not tracked (assumed N_2), [59] ^b
R14: $N_2(A) + N_2(A) \rightarrow N_2(B) + N_2(v)$	7.7×10^{-11}	Vib. state not tracked (assumed N_2), [59] ^b
R15: $e + N_2 \rightarrow N_2 + e$	$f(E)$	Lumped state—see text, [55] ^a
R16: $N_2^+ + 2N_2 \rightarrow N_4^+ + N_2$	5×10^{-29}	[59] ^c

^a From Bolsig+, ϵ in eV.^b Units of $cm^3 s^{-1}$, T_e in K.^c Units of $cm^6 s^{-1}$.^d Units of $1/s^{-1}$.

A floor density of $10^9 m^{-3}$ is used for all charged species to emulate the effects of cosmic rays induced, background ionization. These values also correspond to the floor density for each species respectively. The secondary electron emission (SEE) coefficient for the electrode and dielectric boundaries is set to 10^{-2} . The influence of these parameters on the discharge evolution is rather small and a parametric study falls outside the scope of this work—a discussion is provided in section 6.

4. The case under study, computational and initial parameters

The computationally domain mimics the experimental setup: a 60 cm long quartz tube is used with inner diameter, 17.5 mm, outer diameter, 21.5 mm, with metallic electrodes at the ends of the tube. The HV electrode has a 25 mm long conical shape with a cone angle of 30 degree. The low-voltage (grounded) electrode is plate-shaped. Thus, while the inter-electrode gap, L , equals the tube's length (60 cm), the axial distance between the HV electrode's apex and the ground electrode is approx. 56.7 cm. The tube is surrounded by a cylindrical, grounded, metallic shield of inner diameter 60 mm. Figure 3 presents an illustration of the computational domain and relevant dimensions.

In the experiments, a pulse of 13.5 kV amplitude, 25 ns duration at half width and 6 ns rise time was supplied from a HVG

with a 40 Hz repetition frequency. In the simulations, we apply a similar waveform (one pulse) but with amplitude of 27 kV to emulate the constructive interference between the forward and backward propagating pulses. In table 3, we summarize the geometrical and operational conditions for the simulations (see also figure 3).

The computational mesh is an unstructured one, created in the Gmsh [61] software, properly refined near the electrodes and near the dielectric surface. It consists of 589.445 triangular cells. The minimum cell size is approximately $10 \mu m$ at the 'boundary layer' zone near the electrodes and adjacent to the dielectric surface in order to resolve all plasma-related aspects such as sheaths and cathode layer formation. The computational mesh at the region around the HV electrode tip is shown in figure 3. The domain has been decomposed in 32 sub-domains and the calculations were run on a local HPC workstation (Dell PowerEdge R7515) over 32 computational units (AMD EPYC 7352), leveraging MPI-parallelism.

5. Results and discussion

Figure 4 presents an example of the synchronized voltage and calculated current waveforms for nitrogen, 10 Torr pressure. The voltage waveform is the initial data of the problem, while the current waveform is calculated during the simulations. Different shapes of the current are observed for negative and positive polarity: the current behavior at negative polarity

Figure 3. Illustrative graph of the discharge tube. The axisymmetric computational (CPU) domain corresponds to the upper half. Dimensions not in scale. The unstructured mesh refinement near the HV electrode tip is also shown. Similar refined regions are used near the dielectric surface and both electrode surfaces.

Table 3. Geometrical and operational conditions for the simulations.

HV electrode half-angle	$\theta = 15$ degrees
Discharge tube internal diameter	$D_1 = 17.6$ mm
Discharge tube external diameter	$D_2 = 21.6$ mm
Shielding cage diameter	$D_3 = 60$ mm
Inter-electrode gap	$L = 60$ cm
Relative permittivity of dielectric	3.2

is similar to the surface discharge, when two peaks of different polarity are observed at rising front and falling edge of the high voltage pulse; the current at positive polarity is high after the front. Typical values for current for both polarities are tens of A.

5.1. FIW velocity

Velocity, measured as a gradient of the electric charge along the DT [62] and maximum velocity calculated from the propagating front and the position of maximum total charge (in absolute value), are presented together for negative and positive polarities in figure 5. Increase of the FIW velocity up to a few Torr and then decrease is confirmed by results of the modeling. A reasonable agreement between the calculated and the measured absolute values of the velocity for negative polarity and a quantitative agreement for positive polarity are clearly seen. Typical values of the FIW propagation speed along the tube are 2–4 cm per nanosecond.

We note here that (i) at negative polarity, a double structure of the ionization wave, with a lower amplitude (‘a precursor’) has been observed [13]; (ii) the calculated values have been extracted only from the saved output data from the simulations and not at every time step (to reduce the generated data and due to storage limitations) and as such, the maximum velocities reported here might deviate slightly from the reality. This fact also can explain the small jump observed at 8 Torr under positive polarity.

In any case, the observed trends and orders of magnitude are quite satisfactory when compared with the experimental findings. We also need to emphasize that the calculated velocities

represent the maximum velocity of the FIW: under most of the conditions studied here, the calculated FIW velocity quickly increases to the maximum value and then slowly decays during its propagation, thus the velocity is non-constant.

The optimum pressure for development of a nanosecond discharge for given amplitude of the HV pulse, nitrogen pressure and the DT diameter is about 5 Torr. The trends observed in the numerical results (which are in good agreement with the experimental data) suggest a rather complex dependence of the propagation speed on the plasma structure and the discharge main parameters (electric field, plasma density etc). As we will see in the following sections, under different polarities and different background pressures, the plasma development and properties differ significantly which renders a straightforward explanation of the FIW speed behavior difficult to obtain. Nevertheless, we can extract some interesting information based on the theoretical work [23]. Therein, the authors provide analytical self-similar solutions of the (averaged over the cross-section) problem of high-speed ionizing wave (FIW) propagation in long shielded tubes. A rather simple equation is then provided to describe the FIW speed:

$$v_{\text{FIW}} = \frac{\phi_f \nu(T_e)}{E_0 e} \quad (17)$$

In the above formula, ϕ_f , E_0 and $\nu(T_e)$ are the electrical potential, the maximum of the electric field and the ionization frequency at the FIW front, respectively, while e is the base of the natural logarithm. Note that we have used the electron temperature dependence of the ionization frequency, $\nu(T_e)$, due to our LEA modeling approach. All these parameters are direct outputs of our simulations and can be used to plot the analytical dependence of the FIW speed over pressure for both polarities. This is shown in figure 6, which demonstrates a good qualitative agreement with the calculated values from the simulations.

Our calculations (see following sections for details) show that, for a negative polarity FIW, the potential ϕ_f and the maximum electric field at the front, E_0 , increase monotonically with pressure by nearly an order of magnitude, while their ratio remains constant. Consequently, the speed of the FIW front is approximately proportional to the ionization frequency $\nu(T_e)$. Will note that, despite their increase, the potential and electric

Figure 4. Experimental voltage waveforms (orange dashed curves), used as applied voltage in the numerical solver; calculated current through the discharge cell, (solid blue curves). Measurements are made by capacitive probe; the velocity is calculated by the 0.5 level from the amplitude of the signal. Nitrogen, pressure 10 Torr.

Figure 5. Experimental (filled symbols) and calculated (half-filled symbols) velocities of the fast ionization wave (FIW) propagation. Nitrogen, (a) negative polarity; (b) positive polarity. Reproduced with permission from [62].

field remain approximately half of the corresponding values observed for positive polarity. This behavior reflects the fact that, under a negative polarity pulse, electrons propagate ahead of the FIW front region. With this pre-ionization, the FIW can propagate even in a relatively low field.

For a positive polarity FIW, electrons move backward, to the plasma bulk. Both the potential ϕ_f and the maximum electric field at the front, E_0 , remain nearly constant over the studied pressure range. With the electric field being constant, the reduced electric field E/N decreases by an order of magnitude between 1 and 10 Torr. The calculations reveal a sharp drop in T_e with pressure increase. Consequently, at low pressures, ionization efficiency, electron density, and FIW speed remain low, and E/N exceeds the optimal values for ionization. At high pressures, on the right decaying branch of v_{FIW} , E/N falls below the optimal one for ionization, with the maximum value of v_{FIW} occurring at an intermediate pressure.

So for both polarities of the HV pulse, the main parameter influencing the FIW propagation speed according to formula (17) is the ionization frequency $\nu(T_e)$ at the FIW

front. Discrepancies in the absolute values of the FIW speed between the analytical formula and results of calculations (see figure 5) can be attributed to the choice of values at the FIW front and limitations of the self-similar analytical approach.

The electron density as a function of pressure exhibits a maximum at approximately the same pressure as the FIW front speed. On the right decaying branch of v_{FIW} , the conditions are optimal for dissociation through the excitation of molecular electronic levels, with the dissociation degree reaching its maximum at a higher pressure than the FIW speed maximum. Experimental data on electron density measured via microwave interferometry [63] and O_3 production measured via UV absorption [64] strongly support this reasoning regarding the dependence of discharge parameters on pressure and the relative positions of the maxima.

To trace the most characteristic interval of the FIW propagation and retrieve information on discharge aspects that influence the FIW speed for both polarities, simulation results are presented below for 1, 5 and 10 Torr.

Figure 6. Analytical velocities (equation (17)) of the fast ionization wave (FIW) for positive and negative polarity versus pressure.

5.2. Spatiotemporal distribution of electric field, electron temperature, charged species densities and density of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$

Calculated spatiotemporal distribution, represented as $x-t$ diagrams, of the electron and ion densities, density of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$, the longitudinal component of the reduced electric field $|E_z|/N_g$ and the electron temperature T_e for negative and positive polarities of the HV pulse are presented and discussed in this section. All values are taken on the axis of the discharge, at $r=0$. The point $(Z;t) = (0;0)$ corresponds to the HV electrode, $Z = 60$ cm corresponds to the low-voltage electrode, and $t > 30$ ns corresponds to the falling edge of the HV pulse. Note that for visualization purposes, the graphs of electron temperature and reduced electric field are excluding the sheath zones near the electrodes (where very high values are observed). Similarly, minimum values of E/N , T_e and species density limited to 0.1 Td, 0.1 eV and 10^{14} m^{-3} respectively, also for visualization purposes, while maximum values for species densities are limited to 10^{20} m^{-3} (only in the cases of positive polarity such limitation acts in the near-electrode regions).

5.2.1. Negative polarity. Figures 7–9 show the spatiotemporal behavior for negative polarity discharge at gas pressure $P = 1, 5$ and 10 Torr respectively. The discharge onset and formation of high electron density is clearly seen in the interval 5–10 ns, depending on pressure. The discharge velocity is higher at the beginning, decelerating as the FIW propagates along the tube. This is a distinctive feature of the negative polarity discharge, which is more pronounced for low pressures: for example, for $P = 5$ torr, the discharge velocity gradually decreases from 2 cm ns^{-1} (at 13.64 ns) to 0.68 cm ns^{-1} (at 32.1 ns) as the FIW develops in the gap.

The front of the FIW, or a region with a high electric field, lasts a few nanoseconds, in agreement with experimental observations. The duration of this high peak of E-field is a

function of pressure, decreasing from 5–10 ns at 1 Torr to 1–2 ns at 10 Torr. At 1 Torr, a plasma sheath with thickness of approx. 0.6 cm is clearly visible near the left electrode (at distance $z = 0$). The electron density produces mainly in the FIW front. The front represents a gradient of both electron and N_2^+ ions, with a length of approximately 4 cm. Behind the FIW front, the quasi-neutral plasma body sustains electron and N_2^+ densities in the order of 10^{11} – 10^{12} cm^{-3} . Electron-ion recombination for such a period of time can be disregarded and the decrease of the level excitation rate is caused by a decrease of the electron energy. Hence, the electron density monotonically builds up during the impulse and becomes stationary. Behavior of density of N_2^+ ions repeats the behavior of electrons; the densities of other ions are much lower.

In the plasma bulk, increasing electron density, and still high despite the decreasing electric fields, lead to efficient excitation of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ -state, producing a major part of optical emission of the nanosecond moderate pressure discharges in nitrogen. The delay between the FIW front and $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ excitation is clearly seen. The density of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ -state inside the plasma bulk is in the order of 10^{11} cm^{-3} . The picture corresponds completely to experimental observations of paper [17] describing population of nitrogen molecule electron states and structure of the FIW.

The calculated reduced electric field and electron temperature inside the plasma bulk are in the order of 10–100 Td and 1–5 eV while the FIW front sustains quite high fields in the order of 1000 Td and higher, with electron temperatures in the 10–30 eV range. Such high values of E/N are in agreement with several modeling results [32–34].

5.2.2. Positive polarity. Figures 10–12 show $x-t$ diagrams of the electron and ion densities, density of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$, the longitudinal component of the reduced electric field $|E_z|/N_g$ and the electron temperature T_e for positive polarity of the HV pulse. As everywhere in this work, the discharge is in nitrogen.

Similar to the negative polarity discharge, the discharge starts from the HV electrode at approximately 8 ns. Differently from the negative polarity, the FIW propagates at an almost constant velocity, especially for lower pressures. Similar to the negative polarity, the FIW front presents a gradient of both electron and N_2^+ ions, with a length of approximately 4 cm. Behind the FIW front, the quasi-neutral plasma body sustains electron and N_2^+ densities in the order of 10^{12} – 10^{13} cm^{-3} , with higher values observed at lower pressure. $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ distribution follows the FIW development, but densities inside the plasma bulk are higher and in the order of 10^{12} cm^{-3} .

At moderate and higher pressure, and similar to the negative polarity discharge, $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ front presents a weaker gradient with a length of more than 10 cm, owed to a convolution of increasing electron density and decreasing electric field. Even if, similar to the negative polarity discharge, the electric field in the FIW front is much higher than behind the front, the difference between the field in the front and after the front is much higher for positive polarity. The calculated reduced electric field and electron temperature inside the plasma bulk are similar to negative polarity (in the order of 10–100 Td and

Figure 7. Negative polarity at 1 Torr: axial distance vs time contour plot of electron, N_2^+ , $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ species density [m^{-3}], axial component of reduced electric field magnitude [Td] and electron temperature [eV] at $r = 0$. All plots in log-scale.

1–5 eV respectively) but the FIW front sustains substantial higher fields in the order of 10000 Td, resulting to electron temperatures around and even higher than 100 eV. As mentioned also before, such high values of E/N are consistent with several modeling results [32–34]. Without going into details, will note that so high values of electron energy observed in numerical simulation in the FIW front, may indicate the necessity to take into account non-local effects in the front. Non-locality is beyond the scope of this paper, will just mention that the over-population of the EEDF of nanosecond discharge of positive polarity in N_2 at 5 Torr by high energy electrons was indirectly observed in experiments [13].

At $P = 5$ Torr, the calculated FIW propagation speed is substantially higher and equals approximately 3.17 cm ns^{-1} . Owing to this high velocity, the FIW is reaching the grounded electrode in less than 30 ns. At $P = 10$ Torr, the FIW speed slightly decreases, reproducing the experimental observations.

The experimental results on charge behavior in space and time for $P = 5$ Torr nitrogen discharge for both polarities [13] are presented in figure 13. Two major differences are observed in the experiment for negative and positive polarities: (i) the presence, at negative polarity, of the developed precursor—a primary wave of low amplitude which the main wave catches up with only at a distance of ~ 30 cm from the HV electrode;

Figure 8. Negative polarity at 5 Torr: axial distance vs time contour plot of electron, N_2^+ , $\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)$ species density [m^{-3}], axial component of reduced electric field magnitude [Td] and electron temperature [eV] at $r = 0$. All plots in log-scale.

(ii) slowing down of the velocity of this precursor with increasing the distance from the high voltage electrode, while the velocity of the ionization wave initiated by a positive polarity pulse on the HV electrode, is constant. The latter effect is well reproduced by numerical simulations of the present work (compare to figures 8 and 11 respectively).

5.2.3. Temporal profiles of E/N and electron density. It is interesting to compare calculated absolute values of the reduced electric field and the electron density as a function of time with the experimental data available in the literature. As far as CP allows measuring only longitudinal component

of the electric field, E_z , all the discussion below is about the longitudinal component. It is also important to mention that the CP has a space sensitivity function, and experimentally observed peak of the field should be smoother than in reality.

The experimentally measured waveforms of the longitudinal electric field at 13 cm from the HV electrode and of the averaged over the cross-section electron density [13] are presented in figure 14. The duration of the high fields in the front of the FIW is 2–3 ns for any of the polarities. For negative polarity, the peak values of the reduced electric field do not exceed 500 Td, decreasing after the front to approximately 100 Td. For positive polarity, the fields are higher

Figure 9. Negative polarity at 10 Torr: axial distance vs time contour plot of electron, N_2^+ , $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ species density [m^{-3}], axial component of reduced electric field magnitude [Td] and electron temperature [eV] at $r = 0$. All plots in log-scale.

than 1000 Td in the front, decreasing to 40 Td after the front. The electron density is lower at negative polarity, $n_e^{exp} \sim 4 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, while for positive polarity $n_e^{exp} \sim 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$.

Figure 15 shows the same temporal profiles extracted from the numerical simulations. The calculated E/N is noticeably higher at the plasma front for positive polarity compared to negative polarity, which agrees with the experimental data. Similarly, good agreement is observed on the electron density values, which are lower for negative polarity. After the front, the reduced field is decreasing to values close to the ones observed in the experiments and around 100 Td for both

polarities. The build-up of the electron density in numerical modeling is sharper than in the experiment. This might be due to uncertainties on the ionization rate coefficient in the region of very high electric fields (which occur at the FIW front) and the numerical overestimation of this rate (and underestimation of energy losses) which can result to a faster ionization and thus a steeper temporal profile of the electron density. The delay between the field onset and the increase of the electron density is about 3–5 ns in both experiments and modeling results (with slightly shorter delay observed in the experiments), which might be another indicator that in

Figure 10. Positive polarity at 1 Torr: axial distance-time contour plot of electron, N_2^+ , $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ species density [m^{-3}], axial component of reduced electric field magnitude [Td] and electron temperature [eV] at $r = 0$. All plots in log-scale.

moderate E/N values, the reaction rates relevant to ionization are less prone to errors. The differences observed might also be related to the initial ionization levels used in the simulations, an overestimation of which, can result to a faster build-up of the electron density. The higher values of both electron density inside the plasma bulk and electron temperature in the FIW front at positive polarity, lead also to higher values of the photoionization source term which is concentrated at the FIW front (i.e. an order of magnitude difference between positive and negative polarities at 5 torr and at the same time-instant). These aspects can explain the higher velocity observed under positive polarity, as volume ionization (both electron-impact and photo-related) is stronger in this case.

Will now consider more in details the radial distribution of different components behind the FIW front, and how this distribution influences $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ density, and so the optical emission from the discharge).

5.3. Radial distribution of electron density in the nanosecond discharge. Comparison to the experimental discharge appearance measured by optical imaging

5.3.1. Negative polarity. Comparative studies are presented herein for the case of negative polarity. In figure 16, we plot the electron density contours in the whole DT, at $t = 32.68$ ns for different gas pressure.

Figure 11. Positive polarity at 5 Torr: Axial distance vs time contour plot of electron, N_2^+ , $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ species density [m^{-3}], axial component of reduced electric field magnitude [Td] and electron temperature [eV] at $r = 0$. All plots in log-scale.

It is clearly seen that the discharge propagates further with increasing pressure, featuring a less wide sheath near the HV electrode. The radial distribution of the electron density is non-uniform in all pressures, with higher densities observed near the dielectric walls. To shed more light on this, in figure 17, we plot the radial profiles of electron, N_2^+ and $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ densities at $t = 32.68$ ns and at a distance of 6.75 cm from the HV electrode’s tip for different gas pressures.

All species follow the same radial distribution, showing maximum near the dielectric walls. The density gradient is higher at high pressure than at lower ones e.g. at 10 Torr, the plasma density near the dielectric reaches values

of almost $10^{19} m^{-3}$ while at the axis, is one order of magnitude lower. At low pressure (1 Torr) the sheath formed near the dielectric is more pronounced as expected by plasma theory. As the emission relates mainly to the density of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$, the numerical results confirm the experimental observations of higher emission near the walls for negative polarity.

5.3.2. Positive polarity. Comparative studies are presented herein for the case of positive polarity. In figure 18, we plot the electron density contours in the whole DT, at $t = 32.68$ ns for different gas pressure.

Figure 12. Positive polarity at 10 Torr: axial distance vs time contour plot of electron, N_2^+ , $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ species density [m^{-3}], axial component of reduced electric field magnitude [Td] and electron temperature [eV] at $r = 0$. Positive polarity at 10 Torr. All plots in log-scale.

Here, the discharge propagates further with increasing pressure until it reaches a maximum speed, which is then reduced—at 5 Torr the discharge has already filled in the gap at this time-instant, while at 1 and 10 Torr it stops propagating before bridging the gap. The radial distribution of the electron density is rather uniform at 1 Torr while it begins to take a non-uniform profile with increasing pressure. Near the HV electrode, an intense discharge is produced which is in agreement with the experimental emission profiles. As in the negative polarity case above, and to shed more light on this, in figure 19, we plot the radial profiles of electron, N_2^+ and $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ densities at $t = 32.68$ ns and at a distance of 6.75 cm from the HV electrode’s tip for different gas pressures.

Similar to the negative polarity case, all species follow the same radial distribution. In contrast to the negative polarity though, the discharge is more uniform at low pressure, showing maximum near the axis or presenting a smoother electron density gradient. As the pressure increases, the discharge seems to obtain a non-uniform radial profile and approach the distribution of the negative polarity case. The sheaths formed near the dielectric are thicker at all pressure levels in this case.

The change of radial profiles observed between the negative and positive polarities is related to the presence of the dielectric and associated surface charging effects. Similar to nanosecond surface dielectric barrier discharges (DBDs) [65], the effects of surface charge accumulation as well as SEE

Figure 13. Dynamics of charge measured by capacitive probe for FIW developed in 5 Torr N₂:(a) negative polarity, (b) positive polarity. The high voltage electrode tip corresponds to coordinate $x = 0$ cm. Reproduced from [13]. © IOP Publishing Ltd. All rights reserved.

Figure 14. Experimentally measured longitudinal component of the reduced electric field and averaged over the cross-section of the tube electron density at the distance 13 cm from the high-voltage electrode: (a) negative polarity; (b) positive polarity. Nitrogen, pressure 5 torr. Reproduced from [13]. © IOP Publishing Ltd. All rights reserved.

Figure 15. Calculated longitudinal reduced electric field and electron density at the distance 13 cm from the high-voltage electrode. Nitrogen, pressure 5 Torr.

on the dielectric surfaces, which are both dependent on the voltage polarity and thus the orientation of the electric field vectors which dictate charged species transport towards the dielectric tube, seem to play an important role on the discharge dynamics.

The calculated distribution of discharge emission over the cross-section reproduces the main features observed in the experiment. To provide better comparison, figure 20 presents

a direct Abel transform of the calculated radial distribution of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ density taken from figures 17 and 19. The forward Abel transform is done using the online PlasmAbel software [66]. The ICCD images of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u) \rightarrow N_2(B^3\Pi_g)$ emission in air are shown in the same figure (see section 2 for more details). Excellent qualitative correlation between ICCD imaging and $[N_2(C^3\Pi_u)]$ calculations is observed. Will underline that, in spite of visible ‘homogeneity’ with a weakly expressed

Figure 16. Electron density contours [m^{-3}] for different gas pressure at $t = 32.65$ ns. Negative polarity. Min/max values are limited to 10^{14} m^{-3} and $5 \times 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-3}$ respectively for visualization purposes.

Figure 17. Negative polarity: radial profiles of electron, N_2^+ and $\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)$ densities at $t=32.68$ ns and at a distance of 6.75 cm from the HV electrode for different gas pressure.

minimum, at negative polarity on the HV electrode, the discharge develops near walls, leaving the near-axis part ‘empty’. The difference between the density of particles produced near the walls and on the axis can reach an order of magnitude or

more (see figure 17), and this should be taken into account in any measurements of the density of active species. At positive polarity of the HV electrode, especially at low pressures, the discharge develops along the axis, the distance between a

Figure 18. Electron density contours [m^{-3}] for different gas pressure at $t = 32.65$ ns. Positive polarity. Min/max values are limited to 10^{14} m^{-3} and $5 \times 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-3}$ respectively for visualization purposes.

(a) $p=1$ Torr

(b) $p=5$ Torr

(c) $p=10$ Torr

Figure 19. Positive polarity: radial profiles of electron, N_2^+ and $\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)$ densities at $t = 32.68$ ns and at a distance of 6.75 cm from the HV electrode for different gas pressure.

Figure 20. Direct Abel inversion of calculated $N_2(C)$ density profiles in pure N_2 for (a) the negative polarity discharge, the calculated profiles are taken from figure 17; (b) the positive polarity discharge, the calculated profiles are taken from figure 19. ICCD images for corresponding polarity and pressure experiments in air taken from figure 2 are presented in the same figure (see text for details).

quasi-neutral plasma and the walls (sheath thickness) can reach 2 mm for a tube diameter of 20 mm.

6. Discussion

As in any modeling approach, several parameters might influence the numerical results. Although the scope of this study is not to provide a detailed parametrization and assessment of the numerical accuracy versus the large number of uncertainty and error sources in plasma modeling (which would require a separate and demanding study on its own, including aspects on the discretization schemes), we summarize below and elaborate on the main assumptions used in our model as well as limitations, focusing on physical aspects.

- (i) Memory effects, seed electrons and pre-ionization mechanisms: the FIW dynamics depend strongly on the existence of residual charges (memory effect) in the discharge gap [67] as well as preionization and various seed electron mechanisms [68]. A memory effect owed to the repetitive pulse and accumulation of electron-ion pairs between each pulse is unlikely in the case studied here, as the pulse repetition frequency is rather low (40 Hz) and the electron-ion recombination time scale is much shorter (in the microsecond range). Nevertheless, seed electrons can be generated via other mechanisms [69]: in nitrogen, positive ions produced by collisions of long-lived metastable atoms and vibrationally excited species can bombard the cathode and generate secondary electrons in the early afterglow. In addition and in late afterglow, nitrogen atoms (especially $N(^4\Sigma)$ which recombination time lasts several hours) produced by collisions between the aforementioned molecules and the quenching with neutral species or collisions with the dielectric walls of metastable atoms, can also recombine on tube walls and electrodes to produce metastable $N_2(A^3\Sigma_u^+)$ molecules. These metastable molecules can also release electrons from the electrode through collisions [70, 71]. The role of remnant surface charge on the dielectric surface might also influence

the FIW dynamics especially at high repetition rates. In addition, pre-ionization mechanisms owed to high-energy electrons (runaway), x-rays, and ultraviolet radiation can also provide means for elevated electron density ahead of the FIW front [31, 38, 72]. In [38], the authors show that both low and high (producing ionizing x-rays) energy runaway electrons, can ionize the background gas. Such runaway electrons can be produced near the high voltage electrode or at the FIW front, where electric fields are very high and owed to their very long energy relaxation length can travel in a nearly collision-less environment [73] and provide uniform ionization inside the tube.

In our simulations, we chose a relatively high initial electron (and ion) density to emulate the existence of residual and seed electrons between each pulse and the effect of pre-ionization caused by fast electrons. In our (hydrodynamic) modeling approach, such fast electrons cannot be modeled and as such we have assumed that during the pulse, fast electrons are indeed produced near the HV electrode and/or at the FIW head and ionize the tube volume uniformly and instantaneously. The initial density has been chosen so that we ensure the initiation and propagation of the FIW with speeds close to the ones observed in the experiments. We have confirmed that lower initial densities, produce slower FIWs compared to experiments, which strengthens our hypothesis and choice of rather high preionization/remnant charges inside the tube—e.g. our simulations show that for an initial electron density of 10^{12} m^{-3} (for the positive polarity 5 torr case) leads to a reduction of the FIW speed by approx. 30%. Acknowledging that the assumption made is quite simplified, it is common in similar modeling attempts (with different initial densities considered) and allows us to obtain important insights on the FIW dynamics. A fully kinetic or hybrid kinetic-fluid approach could allow the self-consistent modeling of electrons with different energies and the various pre-ionization mechanisms. The modeling of several pulses (i.e. timescales of several seconds) with a more detailed chemistry and surface reaction mechanisms, could also allow to calculate

the densities and distribution of long-lived species and various seed mechanisms. Both approaches present severe limitations in multi-dimensional simulations due to their extremely demanding nature in terms of computational time.

- (ii) Plasma chemistry: as noted in section 3.1, the plasma chemistry model is quite simplified but is adequate to describe the first nanoseconds of the FIW development and propagation. In this timescales (lower than 50 ns), the main reactions that influence the FIW dynamics are the electron impact reactions (R1–R6). Transitions between vibrational states have been included in order to obtain a fair estimation of the $N_2(C^3\Pi_u)$ population which can be directly compared with the experimental profiles. The error induced by the lumping procedure of excited states should be definitely studied in more detail, but for the purposes of this study (the FIW dynamics) we consider a fair trade between accuracy of electron losses and computational efficiency (as tracking of each excited species would increase substantially the computational time needed for each simulation). In addition, associative ionization has been excluded from this set. Despite the important role of these reactions (which involve collisions between excited states) on the electron population during the afterglow phase [34], our focus on the discharge phase renders this influence rather weak. A more detailed chemistry model is necessary in order to accurately describe the early and late afterglow phases of the discharge, which should not only include the aforementioned separate species and reactions, but also additional reactions between heavy species (including processes involving metastables).
- (iii) Photoionization: photoionization is another possible mechanism of seed electrons in front of the FIW, able to sustain its propagation (especially under positive polarity) even in pure nitrogen [74]. Our simulations show that the photoionization source term ranges between $10^{22} - 10^{24} \text{ m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$ (depending on pressure and polarity) near the FIW front, which means that in a nanosecond timescale it can produce electron densities of $10^{13} - 10^{15} \text{ m}^{-3}$, promoting the FIW propagation and balancing electron losses.

In [34], the authors studied the influence of photoionization (using a plasma fluid model) on the FIW dynamics in capillary tube at 27 mbar. They show that a background ionization on the level of $4-6 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-3}$ is adequate to approximate the FIW propagation dynamics even without considering photoionization. In our case, and under the initial conditions used (electron density on the order of 10^{14} m^{-3}), we have confirmed (running cases without photoionization) that photoionization does not strongly modify the FIW dynamics or the radial distribution of the species—the initial electron density is high enough to play the role of a background seed source. Nevertheless, photoionization leads to a slightly higher propagation velocity especially under negative polarity, which approaches closer the experimental findings. Owing to the uncertainties of seed electron mechanisms (as explained at the first

point of this section), the level of residual charges present inside the DT or its preionization, it is not straightforward to conclude on the influence of photoionization on the phenomena studied here. In addition, the spectrum emission intensity, the photoionization yield and the absorption coefficients used to calculate the fitting coefficients (table 1) contain uncertainties which might lead to errors in the photoionization source term. Nevertheless, we have chosen to include this mechanism and accept such errors, in order to provide a more complete description of the FIW propagation and integrate the non-local character of the photoionization mechanism in our model. A detailed analysis of the influence of photoionization (and the fitting parameters) on the FIW dynamics is left for a future study, where the combined effect of residual charges and electron seed with the photoionization effect should be examined.

- (iv) SEE and other surface kinetics: surface kinetics are only included here as direct recombination of all charged species in dielectric and metal surfaces. We employ a typical formulation (under the plasma-fluid modeling approach) for including the SEE kinetics through the positive ion boundary flux. Nevertheless, the SEE is subject to uncertainties in both the ion-impinging energy, the secondary electron energy, as well the values of the coefficient itself (which depends on the surface material and structure). We have confirmed that the influence of the SEE coefficient in the obtained results is negligible (by removing SEE effects and by adjusting the SEE coefficient to different values in the $10^{-6}-10^{-2}$ range)—a result which is expected as SEE should not influence the FIW in the short timescales studied herein—FIW development and propagation mainly relates to the high values of E/N found at the FIW front under the nanosecond time-scales of the HV pulse and any preionization/seed electron mechanisms. That said, the role of SEE in long time-scales (in late afterglow between pulses) might be important for generating memory effects as described at the beginning of this section.

7. Conclusions

In this study, FIWs propagating along a cylindrical coaxial discharge setup are investigated using 2D-axisymmetric numerical modeling. FIWs are initiated by a single nanosecond pulse with a 27 kV amplitude applied to the HV electrode. The pulse has a FWHM of 25 ns and a rise time of 4 ns, corresponding to a voltage increase rate of $\partial U/\partial t \approx 6 \text{ kV ns}^{-1}$. Both negative and positive polarity pulses are considered. The study examines pressures ranging from 1 to 10 Torr in molecular nitrogen. The numerical results are validated against available experimental data.

Consistent with experimental observations, the numerical modeling reveals a characteristic temporal behavior of the FIW front: the electron density builds up following a sharp and brief (a few nanoseconds) peak in the electric field. The peak electric field reaches approximately 10^3 Td , with values

20%–30% higher for positive polarity pulses. After the front, the field drops to around ~ 100 Td. The electron density behind the FIW front is in the range of $10^{11} - 10^{12} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for FIWs initiated by negative polarity pulses and $10^{12} - 10^{13} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for FIWs initiated by positive polarity pulses. The synchronized waveforms of $E/N(t)$ and $n_e(t)$ observed in experiments are reproduced by the numerical modeling.

For both polarities, FIWs originate at the HV electrode and propagate along the tube. The numerically obtained FIW velocities are in good agreement with experimental results, exhibiting a clear maximum as a function of pressure. For a given voltage amplitude and DT diameter, this maximum occurs at 5–6 Torr, with FIW velocities of 2–3 cm ns^{-1} for negative polarity pulses and 3–4 cm ns^{-1} for positive polarity pulses.

Furthermore, the radial distributions of densities of electrons, ions and $\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)$ molecules are analyzed. The numerical modeling indicates similar radial distributions for $n_e(t)$ and $[\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)]$ for all considered cases, while a well-pronounced sheath with a non-compensated charge of positive ions is observed near the tube wall. The sheath thickness reaches about 2 mm at $P = 1$ Torr for a positive polarity pulse. The density of $\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)$ reaches $10^{11} - 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, with higher values for positive polarity pulses. The pressure-dependent radial distribution of optical emission is well explained by the modeling and shows a good agreement with experimental observations. At negative polarity, the FIW in nitrogen develops near the tube walls, resulting in electron and $\text{N}_2(\text{C}^3\Pi_u)$ densities in the tube center that can be an order of magnitude lower. At positive polarity and low pressures, the significant sheath thickness creates the impression that the FIW propagates in a beam-like mode along the tube axis.

Thus, the proposed modeling approach successfully reproduces key features of FIW development in nitrogen at moderate pressures and can be used as a valuable tool for optimizing nanosecond discharge experiments. Further parametrization for a broader pressure range, different gas mixtures (e.g. air), tube geometries (e.g. diameter to length ratio) and pulse characteristics as well as investigation of the sensitivity of the results to chosen parameters (namely the chosen plasma-chemistry set) are left for future studies. A detailed benchmarking between various modeling approaches able to describe the FIW dynamics versus experimental datasets, would be an essential step in the future to create a mapping of validity range and error estimates for each of these methods.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researchers. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the European Union Project CAIPIRINH3A, under the GA Number 101191768. Views

and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The work of S M Starikovskaia was also partially supported by the Energy4Climate Interdisciplinary Center (E4C) of IP Paris and Ecole des Ponts ParisTech in the framework of the 3rd Programme d'Investissements d'Avenir [ANR-18-EUR-0006-02] and by Cellule Énergie du CNRS (PEPS 2024 Project ZEPHiR).

ORCID iDs

Konstantinos Kourtzanidis <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9496-7428>

Svetlana M Starikovskaia <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6954-7336>

References

- [1] Goldberg B M, Hoder T and Brandenburg R 2022 Electric field determination in transient plasmas: *in-situ* & non-invasive methods *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **31** 073001
- [2] Hay M, Parajuli P and Kulatilaka W D 2023 Simultaneous detection of three chemical species (no, o, o₂) using a single broadband femtosecond laser *Proc. Combustion Institute* vol 39 pp 1435–44
- [3] Starikovskiy A and Aleksandrov N 2013 Plasma-assisted ignition and combustion *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* **39** 61–110
- [4] Starikovskaia S M 2014 Plasma-assisted ignition and combustion: nanosecond discharges and development of kinetic mechanisms *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **47** 353001
- [5] Ju Y and Sun W 2015 Plasma assisted combustion: dynamics and chemistry *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* **48** 21–83
- [6] Leonov S B, Adamovich I V and Soloviev V R 2016 Dynamics of near-surface electric discharges and mechanisms of their interaction with the airflow *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **25** 063001
- [7] Samimy M, Webb N and Esfahani A 2019 Reinventing the wheel: excitation of flow instabilities for active flow control using plasma actuators *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **52** 354002
- [8] Limanowski R, Yan D, Li L and Keidar M 2022 Preclinical cold atmospheric plasma cancer treatment (review) *Cancers* **14** 3461
- [9] Kunishima Y, Takashima K and Kaneko T 2019 Apparent reduced electric field control with nanosecond pulse width in a dc discharge for nitrogen vibrational excitation *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* **58** 060908
- [10] Thomson J J 1893 *Researches in Electricity and Magnetism* (Clarendon)
- [11] Vasilyak L M, Kostyuchenko S V, Kudryavtsev N N and Filyugin. I V 1994 High-speed ionization waves at an electric breakdown *Phys.-Usp.* **163** 263–86
- [12] Anikin N B, Pancheshnyi S V, Starikovskaia S M and Yu Starikovskii A 1998 Breakdown development at high overvoltage: electric field, electronic level excitation and electron density *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **31** 826
- [13] Anikin N B, Starikovskaia S M and Yu Starikovskii A 2002 Polarity effect of applied pulse voltage on the development of uniform nanosecond gas breakdown *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **35** 2785
- [14] Anikin N B, Starikovskaia S M and Yu Starikovskii A 2004 Study of the oxidation of alkanes in their mixtures with

- oxygen and air under the action of a pulsed volume nanosecond discharge *Plasma Phys. Rep.* **30** 1028–42
- [15] Anikin N B, Zavialova N A, Starikovskaia S M and Starikovskii A 2008 Nanosecond discharge development in long tubes *IEEE Trans. Plasma Sci.* **36** 902–3
- [16] Starikovskaia S M, Yu Starikovskii A and Zatsepin D V 1998 The development of a spatially uniform fast ionization wave in a large discharge volume *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **31** 1118
- [17] Pancheshnyi S V, Starikovskaia S M and Yu Starikovskii A 1999 Population of nitrogen molecule electron states and structure of the fast ionization wave *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **32** 2219
- [18] Pancheshnyi S V, Starikovskaia S M and Yu Starikovskii A 2000 Collisional desactivation of $N_2(C^3\Pi_u, v = 0, 1, 2, 3)$ states by N_2 , O_2 , H_2 and H_2O molecules *Chem. Phys.* **262** 349–57
- [19] Starikovskaia S M, Anikin N B, Pancheshnyi S V, Zatsepin D V and Yu Starikovskii A 2001 Pulsed breakdown at high overvoltage: development, propagation and energy branching *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **10** 344
- [20] Starikovskaia S M, Anikin N B, Pancheshnyi S V and Yu Starikovskii A 2002 Time-resolved emission spectroscopy and its applications to the study of pulsed nanosecond high-voltage discharges *Selected Research Papers on Spectroscopy of Nonequilibrium Plasma at Elevated Pressures (Proceedings of Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers vol 4460)*, ed N O Vladimir (SPIE) pp 63–73
- [21] Naidis G V, Tarasenko V F, Yu Babaeva N and Lomaev M I 2018 Subnanosecond breakdown in high-pressure gases *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **27** 013001
- [22] Ebert U, van Saarloos W and Caroli C 1996 Streamer propagation as a pattern formation problem: planar fronts *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **77** 4178
- [23] Sinkevich O A and Gerasimov D N 2000 Propagation of super-high-speed ionizing waves in long shielded tubes *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **33** 54
- [24] Verboncoeur J P 2005 Particle simulation of plasmas: review and advances *Plasma Phys. Control. Fusion* **47** A231
- [25] Birdsall C K and Langdon A B 2018 *Plasma Physics via Computer Simulation* (CRC Press)
- [26] Rodríguez-Patiño D F, Ramírez S, Salcedo-Gallo J S, Hoyos J H and Restrepo-Parra E 2020 Implementation of the two-dimensional electrostatic particle-in-cell method *Am. J. Phys.* **88** 159–67
- [27] Brok W J M, Van Dijk J, Bowden M D, Van der Mullen J J A M and Kroesen G M W 2003 A model study of propagation of the first ionization wave during breakdown in a straight tube containing argon *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **36** 1967
- [28] Viegas P, Slikboer E, Bonaventura Z, Garcia-Caurel E, Guaitella O, Sobota A and Bourdon A 2022 Quantification of surface charging memory effect in ionization wave dynamics *Sci. Rep.* **12** 1181
- [29] Takashima K, Adamovich I V, Czarnetzki U and Luggenhölscher D 2012 Development of fast ionization wave discharges at high pulse repetition rates *Plasma Chem. Plasma Process.* **32** 471–93
- [30] Takashima K, Adamovich I V, Xiong Z, Kushner M J, Starikovskaia S, Czarnetzki U and Luggenhölscher D 2011 Experimental and modeling analysis of fast ionization wave discharge propagation in a rectangular geometry *Phys. Plasmas* **18** 083505
- [31] Huang B-D, Carbone E, Takashima K, Zhu Xi-M, Czarnetzki U and Pu Y-K 2018 The effect of the pulse repetition rate on the fast ionization wave discharge *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **51** 225202
- [32] Klochko A V, Starikovskaia S M, Xiong Z and Kushner M J 2014 Investigation of capillary nanosecond discharges in air at moderate pressure: comparison of experiments and 2d numerical modelling *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **47** 365202
- [33] Zhu Y, Starikovskaia S M, Yu Babaeva N and Kushner M J 2020 Scaling of pulsed nanosecond capillary plasmas at different specific energy deposition *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **29** 125006
- [34] Chen X, Zhu Y, Wu Y, Hao J, Ma X and Lu P 2021 Modeling of fast ionization waves in pure nitrogen at moderate pressure *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **30** 065002
- [35] Timshina M, Eliseev S, Kalinin N, Belsky D, Samokhvalov A, Sergushichev K, Smirnov A and Burtsev V 2020 Numerical investigation of capillary discharge initiation by fast ionization waves *J. Electrostat.* **107** 103485
- [36] Wong T, Timoshkin I, MacGregor S, Wilson M and Given M 2024 A computational study on the effects of fast-rising voltage on ionization fronts initiated in sub-mm air and co 2 gaps *Sci. Rep.* **14** 1185
- [37] Levko D and Raja L L 2016 Influence of field emission on the propagation of cylindrical fast ionization wave in atmospheric-pressure nitrogen *J. Appl. Phys.* **119** 153301
- [38] Levko D and Raja L L 2023 Kinetics of the fast ionization waves with runaway electrons *Phys. Plasmas* **30** 073502
- [39] Lepikhin N D, Popov N A and Starikovskaia S M 2018 Fast gas heating and radial distribution of active species in nanosecond capillary discharge in pure nitrogen and N₂:O₂ mixtures *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **27** 055005
- [40] Pavan C A, Rao S R and Guerra-Garcia C 2024 Tutorial: electrical measurements in nanosecond pulsed plasma reactors *J. Appl. Phys.* **57** 305401
- [41] Kourtzanidis K, Dufour G and Rogier F 2020 Self-consistent modeling of a surface ac dielectric barrier discharge actuator: in-depth analysis of positive and negative phases *J. Appl. Phys.* **54** 045203
- [42] Dufour G and Rogier F 2015 Numerical modeling of dielectric barrier discharge based plasma actuators for flow control: the copaier/cedre example *Aerospace Lab* (available at: https://aerospacelab.onera.fr/sites/default/files/2024-01/AL10-05_0.pdf)
- [43] Bourdon A, Pasko V P, Liu N Y, Célestin S, Ségur P and Marode E 2007 Efficient models for photoionization produced by non-thermal gas discharges in air based on radiative transfer and the Helmholtz equations *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **16** 656
- [44] Piskin T, Podolsky V A, Macheret S O and Poggie J 2019 Challenges in numerical simulation of nanosecond-pulse discharges *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **52** 304002
- [45] Grubert G K, Becker M M and Loffhagen D 2009 Why the local-mean-energy approximation should be used in hydrodynamic plasma descriptions instead of the local-field approximation *Phys. Rev. E* **80** 036405
- [46] Yifei Z H U 2020 Photo-ionization parameter calculator release 1.0
- [47] Zhu Y, Yun W and Li J 2020 Photopic: calculate photo-ionization functions and model coefficients for gas discharge simulations (arXiv: 2005.10021)
- [48] Penney G W and Hummert G T 1970 Photoionization measurements in air, oxygen and nitrogen *J. Appl. Phys.* **41** 572–7
- [49] Kourtzanidis K 2023 Full cycle, self-consistent, two-dimensional analysis of a packed bed dbd reactor for plasma-assisted splitting: spatiotemporal inhomogeneous, glow to streamer to surface discharge transitions *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **32** 105016
- [50] Scharfetter D L and Gummel H K 1969 Large-signal analysis of a silicon read diode oscillator *IEEE Trans. Electron Devices* **16** 64–77
- [51] Tuan Dung N, Besse C and Rogier F 2024 An implicit time integration approach for simulation of corona discharges *Comput. Phys. Commun.* **294** 108906

- [52] Hagelaar G J M and Kroesen G M W 2000 Speeding up fluid models for gas discharges by implicit treatment of the electron energy source term *J. Comput. Phys.* **159** 1–12
- [53] Villa A, Barbieri L, Gondola M and Malgesini R 2013 An asymptotic preserving scheme for the streamer simulation *J. Comput. Phys.* **242** 86–102
- [54] Hagelaar G J M and Pitchford L C 2005 Solving the Boltzmann equation to obtain electron transport coefficients and rate coefficients for fluid models *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **14** 722
- [55] database P (available at: www.lxcat.net) (Accessed 28 November 2023)
- [56] Murphy T NM (USA) Los Alamos National Lab 2025 Total and differential electron collision cross sections for O₂ and N₂
- [57] Cinar D 2014 Relativistic electrons in electric discharges *PhD Thesis DTU Space* (available at: <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/relativistic-electrons-in-electric-discharges>)
- [58] Viehland L A and Kirkpatrick C C 1995 Relating ion/neutral reaction rate coefficients and cross-sections by accessing a database for ion transport properties *Int. J. Mass Spectrom. Ion Process.* **149** 555–71
- [59] Kossyi I A, Yu Kostinsky A, Matveyev A A and Silakov V P 1992 Kinetic scheme of the non-equilibrium discharge in nitrogen-oxygen mixtures *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **1** 207
- [60] Capitelli M, Ferreira C M, Gordiets B F and Osipov A I 2013 *Plasma Kinetics in Atmospheric Gases* vol 31 (Springer)
- [61] Geuzaine C and Remacle J-F 2020 A three-dimensional finite element mesh generator with built-in pre- and post-processing facilities *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.* **11** 79
- [62] Anikin N B 2000 Experimental study of electrodynamic characteristics of the fast ionization waves in molecular gases *PhD Thesis Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology*
- [63] Aleksandrov N L, Kindysheva S V, Kirpichnikov A A, Kosarev I N, Starikovskaia S M and Yu Starikovskii A 2007 Plasma decay in n₂, co₂ and h₂o excited by high-voltage nanosecond discharge *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **40** 4493
- [64] Starikovskaia S M 1995 Energy distribution over the internal degrees of freedom in gas for a high-voltage nanosecond discharge in the case of o₂ dissociation *Plasma Phys. Rep.* **21** 541–7
- [65] Soloviev V R, Konchakov A M, Krivtsov V M and Aleksandrov N L 2008 Numerical simulation of a surface barrier discharge in air *Plasma Phys. Rep.* **34** 594–608
- [66] Plasmabel: easy Abel transformator for plasma optical measurements (available at: www.plasma-tech.net/plasmabel/)
- [67] Zhao Z and Li J 2020 Repetitively pulsed gas discharges: memory effect and discharge mode transition *High Voltage* **5** 569–82
- [68] Ionikh Y Z 2020 Electric breakdown in long discharge tubes at low pressure *Plasma Phys. Rep.* **46** 1015–44
- [69] Pejović M M, Nešić N T and Živanović E N 2012 Afterglow processes responsible for memory effect in nitrogen *J. Appl. Phys.* **112** 013301
- [70] Berkowitz J, Chupka W A and Kistiakowsky G B 1956 Mass spectrometric study of the kinetics of nitrogen afterglow *J. Chem. Phys.* **25** 457–66
- [71] Pejović M M, Živanović E N and Pejović M M 2003 Kinetics of ions and neutral active states in the afterglow and their influence on the memory effect in nitrogen at low pressures *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* **37** 200
- [72] Levko D, Gurovich V Tz and Krasik Y E 2012 Numerical simulation of the pre-ionization processes during nanosecond-pulse discharge in nitrogen *J. Appl. Phys.* **111** 013306
- [73] Huang B, Zhang C, Qiu J, Zhang X, Ding Y and Shao T 2019 The dynamics of discharge propagation and x-ray generation in nanosecond pulsed fast ionisation wave in 5 mbar nitrogen *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **28** 095001
- [74] Pancheshnyi S 2014 Photoionization produced by low-current discharges in o₂, air, n₂ and co₂ *Plasma Sources Sci. Technol.* **24** 015023